

Benefit of Digital Literacy for Academic staff and Students of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

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Abstract: This paper discussed the benefits of digital literacy for academic staff and students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper is a review paper that depend secondary data. The secondary data were collected from print and online publications. The paper revealed that lecturers that are digital literate can handle teaching and learning digital facilities and they are able to deploy the digital resources to carry out their teaching, research and community services functions. The paper also showed that students with digital skills can use different digital resources to improve their academic performance in the tertiary institutions. Based on this findings, the paper hereby suggests that government, private institutions and tertiary institutions should provide more digital infrastructure facilities in respective institutions. Students should be given training and retraining programme on the use pf digital facilities for learning.

Keywords: Academic staff, Digital literacy, Tertiary education, Students

Introduction

Tertiary education is defined by National policy on Education (2013) as the education given after Post Basic Education in institutions such as Universities and Inter-University Centres such as the Nigeria French Language Village, Nigeria Arabic Language Village, National Institute of Nigerian Languages, institutions such as Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs), and Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics, and other specialized institutions such as Colleges of Agriculture, Schools of Health and Technology and the National Teachers' Institutes (NTI). Tertiary education offers a broad range of academic disciplines and professional programs, including bachelor's degrees, master's degrees, doctoral degrees, and professional certifications. It focuses on in-depth exploration of subject areas, critical thinking, research skills, and the development of specialized expertise (Proctoredu 2023).

Tertiary institutions is an organized social institutions made up with stakeholders like the students, lecturers (academic staff), non-academic staff and researcher whose responsibilities are lecturing, organization of instructional resources, assessment of students, marking of students' scripts and projects supervision(Ogunode, & Adamu, 2021). According to Edinoh & Wali-Essien (2023), tertiary education is a social agent of progress and development in the society and aids technological advancement. It is designed to help in the development of nations by providing the high as well as the middle level manpower needed for the social, economic and political advancement through the programme of teaching, learning, research and community services. This function places tertiary education at the apex in the ranking of educational institutions and it is designed to accommodate knowledge acquisition and production.

“Tertiary education or higher education covers a wider range of higher learning institutions

including the university. These higher learning institutions could be organized in different ways, commonly within a university and in a separate institution as university and other tertiary learning institutions (Alemu 2018) Tertiary education as a planned and organized educational system designed for the total development of man/woman and for the total transformation of the society through the utilization of teaching, research and provision of community service. The cardinal programme of tertiary institutions includes; teaching, researching and provision of community services (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie (2023). Tertiary education, also called post-secondary education, is any level of education pursued beyond high school, including undergraduate and graduate credentials. These credentials encompass certificates, diplomas or academic degrees. Tertiary education refers to specialized education in a specific field, taken on after finishing high school. Tertiary education is non-compulsory and provided in a specialist institution, usually a college, polytechnic or university. This form of education may be delivered virtually or at a distance (Top-hat, 2023).

From the above, tertiary education is an organized educational system that is consciously designed for manpower production, in-service training and national development. Tertiary education is an education that advances teaching, research and community services for national development. Tertiary education is an education industry that is meant for the production of manpower and national development via implementation of teaching, research and provision of community services. The objectives of tertiary education includes; to provide higher education opportunities via effective teaching, researching and provision community services; to develop produce students with specialized knowledge and skills for solving personal problem and national problem; to prepare student for national workforce and to contribute to societal and community development; to provide academic program of various disciplines; to provide quality instruction in field of studies and to conduct researches to generate new knowledge for national development and to solve complex problems.

Tertiary education is structured to operate with academic staff, non-academic staff and students. They are critical stakeholder in the tertiary institutions. Their specific roles and function in the institutions is key to the attainment of tertiary education goals. The integration of technology into the management and curriculum implementation demands that both academic and students possess digital skills and be knowledgeable in digital technologies. Study.com (2023) observed that in today's rapidly evolving digital landscape, the importance of digital literacy in schools especially tertiary education cannot be overstated. As technology continues to permeate every aspect of our lives, it has become crucial for the lecturers that are nurturing next generation to possess the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate and thrive in this digital world. Academic staff and students with digital literacy can function effectively in the academic environment because they are equips with the technical skills needed for smooth implementation of teaching and learning. It is based on this that this paper seeks to discuss the benefits of digital literacy for academic staff and students of tertiary institutions.

2.0 Literature Review

Academic Staff

Academic staff are teaching staff of higher institutions and their responsibilities

includes; teaching, researching and provision of community service (Musa, 2021). From the above, academic staff in this paper is an individual that is employed in a higher institution to provide the services of teaching, research and community services. Academic staff is a professional engaged in the tertiary institutions to provide academic services that includes teaching, researching and provision of community services. The job functions of an academic staff includes; presentation of lectures, preparation of lecture plan, organization of instructional resources, students assessment, project supervision, script making, record keeping, committee assignment, supervision of examination and practical work execution.

Academic staff job performance

Job performance of lectures could be measured through teachers' job commitment, feelings of job challenges, job meaningfulness and job responsibilities (Hwang, 2017). The key aspects of teaching involve the use of instructional materials, mastery of the subject matter, discipline intervention where teachers or lecturers have full control of both the students and the school in terms of discipline, teaching methods, regular assessment of students, making lesson plans and notes, delivering of lessons in a clear and concise manner, assessment of students, character formation, teachers' participation in co-curricular activities, attending school assembly (Bassey et al, 2011). From above, academic staff job performance refer to the summation of all official responsibilities executed by a lecturer in a higher institution. Academic staff job performance is the degree and extent by which a lecturer carry out the official tasks and functions in the department or faculty.

Students

Students are learners in educational institutions. Studentship started from the early child education to basic education to secondary school education and ends in the higher institutions. Higher institutions students are learners in the higher institutions. Higher institutions students are matured learners. Students in higher institutions are aged from 18 years and above. Students of higher institutions are ready for learning and research. Some of the students of higher institutions are dependent while others are independent (Ogunode, Audu, & Ahaotu, 2020). From the above, student is an individual admitted into an educational institutions to study and to graduate at a specific term after meeting up with the institution' requirement. Student is an individual admitted to school to learn, to acquire skills and to graduate with a certificate. Student in the schools are expected to attend classes, write exams, continuous assessment, do assignment, do project and read. The student is expected to write exam at the end of every term to reveal his or her performance. The academic performance of students refer to the academic output of the students that covers cognitive, affective and psychomotor. Students' academic performance is the extent of achievement attained in all the academic activities in the school at a particular time.

Students' academic performance

Student academic performance refers to the standard which students should be able to know and be able to do (Ijaiya 2004)'. Academic performance refers to how well students can accomplish the classroom task given to them by their teachers or lectures; it is the extent at which they cope with their studies in relation to the stipulated aims and objectives of the school (Munir & Ma'aruf 2020). Academic performance is usually reflected in learner's ability to be able to communicate the knowledge they have acquired within a given period of time verbally or most of the time, to put it down on paper and measured using test or any other valid instrument. It can

also refer to the measure of students' academic output which can be determined by the grade they obtained at the end of a program. However, if student grades are high, such are called high achievers or low achievers (Tsagem & Bello, 2022). Academic performance is influenced by several factors, meaning that there are multiple causes that can explain variations in it, where in general, these factors can be classified as internal, that is, those that are directly related to the student (such as their age or health status), or external (such as the relationship with teachers and peers, university quality, etc.), where it is important to note that these factors do not have the same importance, since it has been observed that internal factors are those that most affect the performance of university students (Martínez & Ferreira, 2023).

It is a constantly changing process that reflects progress in learning, depending on the skill and dedication of the student, which is influenced by the teaching received and is defined as the result of the skills that facilitate success during their period of study, reflected in a final note that measures their level of knowledge acquired and commonly considered as an indicator of the individual skills and intelligence of the student in their academic activities (Quispe, 2023). Academic performance, is the achievement of the defined purposes in the area, the development of competencies in different educational situations, the average score and the percentage value of students approved, where others see it as the development of competencies in different educational situations (Tacilla, Vásquez, Verde, & Colque, 2020). Academic performance of students is the total learning outcome of the students in the educational institutions which includes the knowledge, social and communication skills and ideas acquired and retained through their course of study (Ogunode & Josiah, 2023). Academic performance as far as education is concerned is something which involves a lot of concentration and experiences in an organization which officially aims at encouraging and developing arts, skills and knowledge related to sciences. James (2000) declared that academic performance really involves knowing how much a student has learned. One way by which this can be determined is by use of performance test. Performance test can give students an indication of his progress and act as a reward for his effort or as a spur against under achievement. Academic performance is the students' level of attainment in the grade point average of courses offered in their yearly examination. In other words, it is the outcome of students' assessment through comprehensive, systematic, diagnostic, progressive, formative, summative and cumulative evaluation of what they had gone through in a school setting. It is the main focus in the overall educational performance (Abdul 2002). From the above, students' academic performance in this paper is the total achievement of the students in all academic activities that covers cognitive, affective and psychomotor in the school over a given time. Students' academic performance refer to the academic grade and scores students obtained after assessment (examination and continuous assessment) in the schools which can be satisfactory or not satisfactory.

Digital Literacy

Digital literacy focuses on the ability to find, assess and use information with the aid of digital tools such as social media, web browsers and online discussion boards. Digital literacy is beneficial for students and teachers as it can promote academic growth and teach students how to effectively use digital tools in different areas of their lives. In this article, we discuss what digital literacy in the classroom is and why it's important for students and educators to use (Indeed editorial team 2024). Digital literacy is the ability to understand and use information in multiple formats from wide range of sources when it is presented via computers. A person's ability to perform tasks effectively in a digital environment, Literacy includes the ability to read and interpret media, to reproduce data and images through digital manipulation and to evaluate and

apply new knowledge gained from digital environments (Adeoye, & Adeoye, 2017).

Digital literacy in the classroom refers to having the knowledge and ability to use a broad range of digital tools such as smart phones, tablets and computers for a variety of educational purposes. While in class, students can use these tools to explore content for different subject areas, connect with other students regarding academic topics and to create their own digital content related to the curriculum they're learning in the classroom (Indeed editorial team 2024). Jones-Kavalier and Flannigan (2008) state that digital literacy represents a person's ability to perform tasks effectively in a digital environment; digital means information represented in numeric form and primarily use by a computer, and literacy includes the ability to read and interpret media, to reproduce data and images through digital manipulation and to evaluate and apply new knowledge gained from digital environments.

Digital literacy is having the knowledge and ability to use a broad range of digital tools such as smart phones, tablets and computers for a variety of educational purposes. While in class, students can use these tools to explore content for different subject areas, connect with other students regarding academic topics and to create their own digital content related to the curriculum they're learning in the classroom. In the context of vocational education and training, digital skills are indispensable for trainers offering work-based learning to train their apprentices (Cedefop 2023). To be digitally literate is to have access to a broad range of practices and cultural resources that you are able to apply to digital tools. It is the ability to make and share meaning in different modes and formats; to create, collaborate and communicate effectively and to understand how and when digital technologies can best be used to support these processes. Digital literacy is the skills, knowledge and understanding that enable critical, creative, discerning and safe practices when engaging with digital technologies in all areas of life, studies and career (Adeoye, & Adeoye, 2017; Ogunode, Olowonefa & Ukozor 2025).

According to UNESCO, digital literacy refers to the ability to adequately and meaningfully manage digital technologies to access, organize, understand, integrate, communicate, evaluate and create information, including computer, ICT and media skills, in order to further empower especially young people to have a critical view towards the use of technology and acquire certain skills (UNESCO, 2023). From the above, digital literacy is the ability of an individual to practically deploy digital facilities to solve personal problems and professional problems. Digital literacy is the capacity and ability of a person to use digital facilities to communicate, receive information, send information, search for information, store information and manage information online.

3.0 Method

This study used a quantitative research approach that employed systematic literature review-based method. Literature search method were adopted using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses guidelines (Adnyana, 2023; Paulus et al., 2023). The selection process is illustrated in Figure 1.

Identification of Data from Database

Identification

content Analysis

Include

This study sought to understand and examine phenomena related to the benefits of digital literacy for academic staff and students of tertiary institutions in Nigeria by focusing on previously published scientific literature. The Elsevier, CEON, and Goggle Scholar databases were used to search for articles that matched the keywords "academic staff," "digital literacy," "students," "tertiary education," "academic job performance" and "academic performance." The articles included in this study were original articles; open access; discussed related research questions; published from 2004 to 2023; and came from Scopus Q1-Q4 reputable journals, Science and Technology Index (SINTA) accredited journals (S1-S6), and the Web of Science with core collection. The various research results obtained were then analyzed with regard to the application of the concept of digital literacy at tertiary institutions, at academic staff job performance and at students' academic performance. All the data were descriptively analyzed and are presented in the form of short narratives. (Adapted from Adnyana, Mahendra, & Raza, 2023)

4.0 Data Analysis

Discussion on Benefit of Digital Literacy for Academic Staff and Students of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

4.1 Benefit of Digital Literacy for Academic staff

Enhances job performance

Digital literacy of lecturers in the higher institutions enhance their job performance in the institutions. Digital literacy give lecturers a chance to combine their educational and technological expertise, become more innovative, and apply revamped teaching models that may improve their performance, their self-esteem, their reputation at school; they may have more opportunities for career progression; and thus, may improve their well-being (Cedefop 2023). Many administrative tasks that teachers need to carry out daily may be reduced thanks to technology if teachers know how to use the respective digital tools and improve their job performance (Montes, 2022; Ogunode & Ndayebom, 2023).

Preparing Students for the Future

Lecturers who are digitally literate can model these skills and help students develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and research abilities necessary for future academic and career success (Key 2020). Many jobs in the workforce have technology-related requirements. After high school or college, students may need to meet these qualifications in order to secure employment. Using multiple forms of digital literacy in the classroom can help students feel comfortable completing different digital tasks that employers might ask them to perform in the workplace. As a teacher, you can give your students digital assignments so they can experiment with different online programs and tools they may use in their future careers. Doing this gives your students a chance to familiarize themselves with tools like spreadsheets and word documents, and teaches them how to research credible content (Indeed editorial team 2024)..

Access to Resources

Digital literacy enables teachers to access a vast array of online resources, including research articles, educational videos, and teaching materials. This can enhance their curriculum and provide students with a more comprehensive learning experience. Technology is common in students' daily lives, so utilising different digital mediums such as blog posts, podcasts and networking opportunities provides a modern approach to engaging students in their studies and expanding educational opportunities (Key, 2022; Ogunode, Ayoko, & Orifah, 2023).

Communication and Collaboration:

Lecturers with digital literacy skills can utilize various communication tools (like email, forums, and social media) to collaborate with colleagues, engage with parents, and connect with other educators globally, fostering a community of learning (Key 2020). Teachers incorporate collaboration in their lessons to engage students in the material and to help them have academic discussions with their peers. Digital literacy provides them with even more opportunities for collaboration. Students can create and edit presentations simultaneously on different computers, share and edit notes through cloud-based software, discuss classroom topics through group messaging apps and reply to one another's discussion posts on educational forums. These collaboration methods give teachers the opportunity to teach students how to communicate effectively through the use of digital literacy, which students can continue to use in adulthood (Indeed editorial team 2024).

Assessment and Feedback and Professional Development

Digital tools can streamline assessment processes, allowing for more efficient grading and feedback. Teachers can use online quizzes, learning management systems, and data analytics to track student progress and adapt their teaching strategies accordingly. Staying digitally literate allows teachers to participate in online professional development opportunities, webinars, and courses, keeping them updated with the latest educational trends and technologies.

Enhances student engagement

When teachers implement digital literacy in the classroom, it helps keep students engaged in their schoolwork. Technology is a common factor in their daily lives, so utilizing different digital mediums such as blog posts, podcasts and networking opportunities provides a modern approach to engaging students in the classroom curriculum. For example, rather than writing a summary on an article they read in class, students can create a video summary. This demonstrates their understanding of the article while also allowing them to create original content using digital media (Indeed editorial team 2024).

Applies to most subject areas and fields

Teachers and lecturers can use digital literacy in nearly every subject area. Depending on the subject area they teach, they can implement different digital literacy strategies tailored to the materials their students learn in class. For example, students in a civics class can join full discussions in online communities where they post their thoughts on civics-related topics. This shows them what it's like to be part of a collective group of people, which is a skill they can use long after they graduate from school. Similarly, students in different science classes may need to conduct research on the validity of the information they learned in class. For example, they can learn how to identify biased media and learn which sources to use when looking for valid information (Indeed editorial team 2024). Digital literacy allows teachers and lecturers to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. This includes using educational software, interactive tools, and online resources to create engaging lessons that cater to diverse learning styles (Key 2020).

The study of Instefjord et al.in Ara (2018) showed that the effectiveness of teachers is directly related to their digital competence. A third of educators consider themselves good role

models in the use of information technology. Study by Rodríguez, et al (2024) showed that support a moderate degree of positive correlation of digital competencies and academic performance with an $r_s = 0.546$ and with a significance level $p = 0.000$, where with respect to the coefficient of determination it is shown that digital competency influences 30.5% on the academic performance of university students, while the remaining 69.5% is affected by other socioeconomic factors. Concluding that there is positive correlation and 30.5% of influence of digital competencies with respect to academic performance, where the remaining 69.5% is due to socioeconomic factors such as educational level in parents, economic level, work, sentimental relationship and the management of time dedicated to study.

Salguero et al. (2024) who inspected the relationship between digital competence and academic performance statistically evaluated in higher education students, where the results confirmed a perfect positive correlation between both variables, suggesting that a good mastery of digital skills is associated with adequate academic performance. Ramirez et al. (2022) where the reason for their article was to decree the association of digital competence and academic performance developed in students of a technical educational entity in Peru, where they concluded that there is a connection between digital skills and academic performance, where those students who have a greater management of digital competences, will have a higher academic performance.

Lecturers with digital literacy prepare the instructional resources into e-resources and digital curriculum. Digital curriculum are instruction package in digital platform for teaching and learning. Digital curriculum are curriculum planned and organized in digital platform such classroom portals and learning spaces, E-books and digital textbooks, digital lessons, Pre-recorded and live sessions, online communities or forums, multimedia content (Videos, infographics, websites, and embedded content) and E-learning apps and software (Mural (for visual collaboration), kahoot (for quizzes), or PhET (simulations), web-based platforms, course providers, and courseware for teaching and learning to optimize learning strategies, provide innovative methods, and personalize learning provision. Digital curriculum is a curriculum of instruction that is digital inclined. Digital curriculum enhances personalize learning, suit learning needs, and provide opportunities. Digital curriculum significantly adds to the technological skills and media and digital literacy. By doing tasks online, lecturers can prepare students to use and find the right online tools. Besides, they can better introduce the concepts of privacy and AI applications (Key 2020).

4.2 Benefits of Digital literacy for Students in tertiary institutions

Improve academic performance

When they use digital tools to create their own original content, many of them can understand the material better and are more likely to retain the information (Cedefop 2023). Digital literacy can improve the academic performance of students by allowing them to create content such as presentations, videos and blog posts. When they use digital tools to create their own original content, many of them can understand the material better and are more likely to retain the information. Digital literacy in the classroom allows students to express their ideas and discoveries in inventive ways, all while improving their ability to perform well academically (Indeed editorial team 2024).

Create more opportunities for collaboration

Students can create and edit presentations simultaneously on different computers, share and edit notes through cloud-based software, discuss classroom topics through group

messaging apps and reply to one another's discussion posts on educational forums. These collaboration methods give teachers the opportunity to teach students how to communicate effectively through the use of digital skills, which students can continue to use in adulthood and in their career (edefop 2023).

Digital literacy gives students another way to learn information in a classroom setting. Students can even use their digital literacy skills outside of school and continue to use many of them into adulthood. Digital tools are online resources that make completing tasks simpler. There are numerous digital tools available to students and educators alike. Using most digital devices, students can browse the internet and utilize email, social media, blog posts, networking and discussion boards. Digital literacy gives teachers the chance to teach students to use these tools to their advantage. It also gives students a learning environment where they can practice applying them in an educational setting (Indeed editorial team 2024; Ogunode, Abdulrazak, & Abubakar, 2023; Olatunde, Ogunode, & Eyiolorunse, 2021).

Effective content researches

Students can use the internet to search for a variety of information such as research for an upcoming report or looking up how to conduct an experiment in science class. Using digital literacy in the classroom even teaches students effective strategies for finding credible information. Teachers can help students identify when websites contain biased or misinformed material so they can avoid that information and find reliable content from relevant sources (Indeed editorial team 2024). Through effective teaching strategies, lecturers can teach students how to cite their sources and how to create citations online. Thanks to digital literacy, students can use online plagiarism checkers to verify that they've correctly cited their information. Using digital literacy in this sense gives students the opportunity to learn about the importance of giving someone credit when they use their published work in their own writing (Indeed editorial team 2024). Digital literacy of students can enable them use e-learning platforms, electronic libraries, self-assessment tools, open educational resources (OER) platforms, education management applications, makerspace and 3D applications (Study.com 2023).

With digital literacy, students can leverage the internet and various digital tools to access knowledge and resources. This enhances their learning experiences and promotes independent and lifelong learning. Digital literacy also enhances communication and collaboration skills. In today's interconnected world, effective communication and collaboration are essential skills. With digital literacy, students can communicate and collaborate online, working with others across geographical boundaries and cultural differences. These skills are invaluable in a globalized society where virtual teamwork is increasingly common. Also, Digital literacy promotes digital citizenship and responsible use of technology. Students learn about online safety, privacy, and ethics, developing a sense of responsibility and awareness of the potential risks and challenges associated with the digital world (Study.com 2023;Indeed editorial team 2024).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper discussed the benefits of digital literacy for academic staff and students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The paper revealed that lecturers that are digital literate can handle teaching and learning digital facilities and they are able to deploy the digital resources to carry out their teaching, research and community services functions. The paper also showed that students with digital skills can use different digital resources to improve their academic performance in the tertiary institutions.

Based on this findings, the paper hereby suggests that government, private

institutions and tertiary institutions should provide more digital infrastructure facilities in respective institutions. Students should be given training and retraining programme on the use of digital facilities for learning.

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